

COMPARATIVE ECONOMICS OF NEEM COATED AND NANO UREA USAGE IN COTTON CULTIVATION

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Abstract

The farmers are under the misconception that higher returns could be obtained through higher uses of Fertilizer (neem coated and nano urea). In this regard, the study provides insight into comparative economics of fertilizer (neem coated & Nano urea) use. The results of the study would be useful to both policy maker and farmers of the region in understanding the nature and economic consequence of fertilizer (Neem coated and Nano urea) use. The study pertains to agriculture year 2023-24 and is based on information obtained by 60(neem coated urea users) and 60 (nano urea users) randomly selected cotton cultivators from Akola District. The resource use efficiency analysis clearly indicated that the resources were optimally used as guided by the economic principles. The MVP/MFC ratios were positive for fertilizer (Neem coated and Nano urea). Thus the rise of these resources would maximize the returns from cotton production. The farmers need to be educated and advised about the proper use of these resources particularly fertilizers (Neem coated and Nano urea). Though the fertilizer (neem coated urea) use was high, the farmers in the study area were already using more quantity of fertilizer (neem coated urea) and fertilizer (nano urea) use is less, the farmers in the study area were already using less quantity of fertilizer (nano urea). Therefore there is an urgent need for proper education to the farmers about the balanced use of fertilizer (neem coated and nano urea).

Keywords—Cotton, Fertilizers, cost and return, Neem coated urea, Nano urea, Resource use efficiency, Optimum use

Introduction

The Indian economy has always been based on agriculture, and this will likely to be continue in future too. The world's population is continuously soaring, and an increase in agricultural production remains a most challenging task to feed the 9.8 billion people by the end of 2050. The expansion of area under cultivation is not possible, as arable land is declining. Further, the soil is becoming increasingly deficient in many plant nutrients due to the intensive nature of agricultural production. Therefore, the use of fertilizers is vital for restoring soil fertility. Fertilizer, as an input in agricultural production, assumes a larger significance in terms of maintaining an adequate food grain output given the significance of agriculture in fulfilling the rising food grain requirements of a country with an ever-growing population (FAI, 2015). India ranks second in the world with respect to fertilizer consumption. The success of India's green revolution and eventual independence in the production of food grains were significantly influenced by fertilizers. There are seventeen nutrients that are essential for plant growth and development, but nitrogen (N) is regarded as the most important for optimum vegetative growth and plant productivity. Thus, nitrogen is a critical component of agriculture and accounts for 50% of the world's food production to meet food challenges.

Nano urea is a source of nitrogen, a major essential nutrient required for better growth and development of crops. IFFCO manufactured nano urea liquid, based on nano technology, effectively fulfils crop nitrogen requirement when sprayed at critical crop growth stages. Nano urea contains 4% nitrogen by weight in its nano form. The Government of India included neem coated urea (NCU) a slow release fertilizer, in the fertilizer (content) order, 1985 and made it mandatory for all the indigenous procedures of urea to produce their a hole production of subsidized urea as NCU from 2015. Further, it has taken various steps to promote NCU, with a view to improve soil health status and also realize higher crop yield.

Cotton crop is an important commercial crop and well known to the farming community as 'white gold'. Small and marginal farmers cultivating cotton under different farming situation. Cotton (*Gossypium Spp.*) is one of the most important commercial crop being in many countries. The cotton production in India during 2022-23 is estimated to produce 337.23 lakh bales of 170 kg from 130.49 lakh hectares with a productivity of 439 kg lint/ha as estimated by the Directorate of Economics and Statistics. In vidhrbha Akola, Amrawati, Nagpur, Yavtmal are the major cotton cultivation districts.

Objectives

To estimate the cost and returns of cotton with special reference to neem coated and nano urea.

To estimate resource use efficiency of cotton production

To estimate optimum use in cotton cultivation.

Methodology

The main objective of any scientific investigation is to draw useful conclusion in light of objective of study. In order to get the meaningful conclusion, it is essential for investigator to adopt appropriate method and procedure, keeping this in view, to explain the methodology adopted, and to fulfill the objective of study. It also deals with source of data, type of data, selection of area, selection of farmers, collection of data, and analytical tools used.

A. Nature & source of data:

The present study was undertaken in Akola district of Vidarbha region. The present study is based on the primary data obtained from sample farmers of Akola district. The Four predominantly growing tahsils were selected viz. Akot, Akola, Telhara & Balapur. Five villages were selected from each tahsil and 3 neem coated urea users and 3 nano urea users of Cotton growers were randomly chosen from each village for getting the required information on Cotton cultivation. Thus the study was based on 60 (neem coated urea users) and 60 (nano urea users) randomly selected Cotton growing farmers spread in Akola district for the year 2023- 24.

B. Method of analysis**a. Tabular analysis**

The data was summarized in the form of appropriate tables. The standard cost concept was used to assess the cost, returns and profits from cotton crop cultivation with special reference to neem coated and nano urea in the study area. The percentage and averages were computed and compared to draw meaningful inferences.

b. Production Function analysis:

The Cobb-Douglas production function was estimated to study the resource use efficiency and influence of inputs on Cotton yield.

$$Y = a X_1^{b_1} X_2^{b_2} X_3^{b_3} X_4^{b_4}$$

Where,

Y= Gross income from cotton (Rs/ha)

X₁= Expenditure on seed (Rs/ha)

X₂= Expenditure on labour (Rs/ha)

X₃= Expenditure on fertilizer other than urea and manures (Rs/ha)

X₄=Quantity of urea used (kg/ha)

$a = \text{Constant}$
 $b_1 \text{ to } b_4 = \text{Production elasticity}$
 One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the technical efficiency of Urea (neem coated and nano urea) use through workout the optimum quantity of Urea (neem coated and nano) use. Use of fertilizer i.e on Neem coated urea (NCU) and Nano urea (NU) were measured in physical quantity while other inputs measured in monetary value. The above function was used as logarithmic formation of all variables and written as

$\log Y = \log a + b_1 \log X_1 + b_2 \log X_2 + b_3 \log X_3 + b_4 \log X_4$
 The marginal value product for each input were calculated at the geometric mean levels of the respective resources and geometric mean level of out-put by using following formula,

Marginal value product of $X_i = b_i (Y/X)$

Where,

$Y = \text{Geometric mean of gross income}$

$X_i = \text{Geometric mean of } X_i^{\text{th}} \text{ resources}$

$b_i = \text{Production elasticity of } i^{\text{th}} \text{ resources}$

The marginal value was equated with the marginal factor cost to determine optimum use of resources. To determine optimum quantity

of fertilizer use under the assumption of the profit maximization behaviour the following relationship was used. The marginal physical product (MPP) of urea was equated to the price ratio of urea (NCU and NU) and cotton.

$$\text{MPP} = (dy/dx) = (P_p / P_y)$$

i.e. $b_4 (Y/X) = P_p / P_y$

$$X^* = (b_4 \cdot Y \cdot P_y) / P_p$$

Where,

$X^* = \text{Optimum quantity of urea}$

$b_y = \text{Production elasticity of urea}$

MPP- Marginal physical product of urea

$P_p = \text{unit price of urea (Rs/ha)}$

$P_y = \text{output price of cotton (Rs/Qts)}$

Result And Discussion

Keeping in view the objectives of the study, the data were analysed using suitable techniques. The results obtained from this study have been presented and discuss critically.

a. Cost and returns from Cotton cultivation with special reference to neem coated and nano urea

Table 1 . Per hectare cost and returns from cotton with special reference to neem coated and nano urea

S N	Particulars	Neem coated urea	Nano Urea
1	Yield (Quintal)	17.02	18.12
2	Price / Quintal	7408.33	7425.00
3	Value of main produce	126074.27	134551.22
4	Total produce	126074.27	134551.22
5	Total cost		
a)	Cost 'A ₂ '	63551.84	61778.52
b)	Cost 'B ₂ '	86923.99	86938.34
c)	Cost 'C ₂ '	96117.33	94705.01
d)	Cost 'C ₃ '	105729.06	104175.51
6	Net return over		
a)	Cost 'A ₂ '	62522.42	72772.70
b)	Cost 'B ₂ '	39150.27	47612.87
c)	Cost 'C ₂ '	29956.94	39846.21
d)	Cost 'C ₃ '	20345.21	30375.70
7	Input-output ratio at		
a)	Cost 'A ₂ '	1.98	2.18
b)	Cost 'B ₂ '	1.45	1.55
c)	Cost 'C ₂ '	1.31	1.42
d)	Cost 'C ₃ '	1.19	1.29

It was revealed from the Table. 1 that, for neem coated urea farmers gross returns was worked out to 126074.27 Rs/ha. The net returns obtain at cost A₂, B₂ and C₂ were 62522.42, 39150.27 and 29956.94 Rs/ha. The net returns obtain at cost C₃ was 20345.21 Rs/ha. For nano urea farmers gross returns was worked out to 134551.22 Rs/ha. The net returns obtain at cost A₂, B₂ and C₂ were 72772.70, 47612.87 and 39846.21 Rs/ha. The net returns obtain at cost C₃ was 30375.70 Rs/ha. The input-output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion indicated that, cotton registered a good input-output ratio for neem coated urea farmers 1:1.19 and for nano urea farmers 1:1.29 at cost C₃ means this is a profitable crop.

b. Resource use efficiency in Cotton

The Cobb-Dougllass production function was estimated to analyse the relationship between resources and productivity of Cotton using survey data from sample farmers. The gross realized income expressed in rupees from cotton output was taken as dependent variable while expenditure made on seeds (Rs), labour (Rs) fertilizer other than urea and manures (Rs), and quantity of urea used (Kg/ha) were taken as independent variables. The dependent and independent variables in

production function were defined on per ha basis. The estimated production functions are presented in Table 2. The inputs included in model explained 70.00 per cent of variation in cotton (neem coated urea users) and 73.00 per cent of variation in cotton (nano urea users) output as revealed by the coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2). The summation of production elasticities indicated decreasing returns to scale i.e. for each per cent incremental use of all inputs simultaneously farmers would get less than one per cent of output. The estimated parameters of expenditure on seeds were positively significant at one per cent of probability level for selected farmers indicating that every one per cent increase in seed it would result in increase of gross return by 0.13 per cent. The coefficients of fertilizer other than urea is positive for farmers and but shows non significant. The elasticity of coefficient for neem coated is positive indicating positive effect on gross income, where one per cent increase in neem coated urea application would result in increase of gross income by 0.02 per cent.

The estimated parameters of expenditure on seeds and labours were positive but shows non significant. The coefficients of fertilizer other than urea is negative for farmers. The elasticity of coefficient for nano

urea is positive indicating positive effect on gross income, where one per cent increase in neem coated urea application would result in increase of gross income by 0.01 per cent.

The analysis of production elasticities are indicated the extent of change in output for every per unit increase or decrease in the use of

resources. The scope for re-organization of the resources was also indicated by the production elasticities. However to compute the optimal use of resources, the marginal value products must be compared with their respective marginal factor costs.

Table 2. Estimated Cobb-Douglass production function in Cotton (Neem coated urea and nano urea users) production

Sr.no	Neem coated urea		Nano urea	
	Explanatory Variable	Coefficient	Explanatory Variable	Coefficient
1	Intercept	2.27	Intercept	3.25
2	Expenditure on seed (Rs/ha)	0.13**	Expenditure on seed (Rs/ha)	0.06
3	Expenditure Labour (Rs/ha)	0.42	Expenditure Labour (Rs/ha)	0.5
4	Expenditure on Fertilizer other than urea(Rs/ha)	0.12	Expenditure on Fertilizer other than urea(Rs/ha)	-0.15
5	Quantity of Neem coated urea(kg/ha)	0.02	Quantity of Nano urea(Lit/ha)	0.01
6	Coefficient of multiple determination R^2	0.7	Coefficient of multiple determination R^2	0.73

Note: * * - denotes significance at 1%

b. Marginal value product to marginal factor cost

The production function analysis used to determine the efficiency of resources use was also used for the estimation of marginal value product of the resources. In fact, the Cobb-Douglas function estimated geometric mean level of inputs used to find out the marginal value product. The knowledge of the marginal returns of resources use is useful because it indicates the level of resources and the economical use of resources for the producers by comparing their marginal value product with the marginal factor cost. If this ratio is less than one

indicates the excess use of the particular input and vice-versa. Maximum efficiency of resources occurs when the marginal value product to marginal factor cost is unity.

The Cobb-Douglas function estimates and geometric levels of inputs and outputs were used to estimate the marginal value products of the inputs. The knowledge of the marginal value products of resources facilitates comparison of marginal value product with marginal factor cost of the resources to arrive at optimal use of resources.

Table.3 Ratio of Marginal value product to the marginal factor cost in cotton production

Sr.no	Neem coated urea users				Nano urea users			
	Resources	MFC	MVP	MVP/MFC	Resources	MFC	MVP	MVP/MFC
1	Seed	1	0.18	0.18	Seed	1	0.09	0.09
2	Labour	1	0.48	0.48	Labour	1	0.57	0.57
3	Fertilizer other than urea & Manures	1	0.15	0.15	Fertilizer other than urea & Manures	1	-0.19	-0.19
4	Neem Coated urea	1	0.05	0.05	Nano urea	1	0.16	0.16

It was evident from Table.3. that the ratio of marginal value product and marginal factor cost was positive and more than unity for seeds, labour, fertilizer other than urea, and neem coated urea for the farmers indicating that the resources were underutilized and there was scope for maximizing returns by increasing the use of neem coated urea. It was evident from Table. 3. that the ratio of marginal value product and marginal factor cost was positive and more than unity for seeds, labour and nano urea for the farmers indicating that the resources were underutilized and there was scope for maximizing returns by increasing the use of nano urea. However, the ratio of marginal value product and marginal factor cost was negative in case of fertilizer other than urea & Manures (-0.19), reveals that every rupee of an additional income on Fertilizer other than urea & manures will lead to reduction in gross income by a tune of 0.19 per cent.

c. Optimum quantity of urea requirement

The optimum quantity of urea requirement for cotton production was presented in Table. 4. The optimum quantity of urea (neem coated urea)

required for cotton was estimated to be 83.00 kg/ha. The requirement of urea (neem coated) as estimated through production function. The actual quantity of urea (neem coated) use was high in the sample farmers. As such farmers were found to over use urea(neem coated) by 107.05 Kg per hectare. In other words the farmers spent Rs. 550.26 per ha. extra because of an uneconomical use of urea(neem coated) in cotton farming. Therefore, any increase in urea(neem coated) higher than the optimal level is really not a rational expenditure.

The optimum quantity of urea (nano) required for cotton was estimated to be 3.36 lit/ha. The requirement of urea (nano) as estimated through production function. The actual quantity of urea (nano) use was less in the sample farmers. As such farmers were found to less use urea(nano) by 3.04 lit per hectare. In other words the farmers need to spent Rs. 162.75 per ha. extra because of an economical use of urea (nano) in cotton farming. Therefore, any increase in urea (nano) less than the optimal level is really a rational expenditure.

Table 4: Optimum quantity of urea requirement in Cotton cultivation

Particular	Neem coated urea		Nano urea	
	Kg/ha	cost (Rs/ha)	lit/ha	cost (Rs/ha)

Optimal use	83	1899.04	3.36	1681.1
Actual use	107.05	2449.3	3.04	1518.35
Saving/loss	-24.05	-550.26	+0.33	+162.75

Conclusion

The resource use efficiency analysis clearly indicated that the resources were optimally used as guided by the economic principles. The MVP/MFC ratios were positive for urea (neem coated and nano urea). Thus the rise of these resources would maximize the returns from cotton production. The farmers need to be educated and advised about the proper use of these resources particularly fertilizers (neem coated urea and nano urea).

Though the urea (neem coated) use was high and urea(nano) use was less. Therefore there is an urgent need for proper education to the farmers about the balanced use of urea (neem coated and nano urea).

References

1. **A S Tingare, N V Shende, U T Dangore, And R D Vaidkar 2024**, Comparative Economics Of Drill Paddy Based Cropping Systems In Gadchiroli District, VOL. XIV, ISSUE XXXXX, Feb. To April. 2024 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 79-87.
2. **A.S. Wayal, S. N. Ingle, S. S. Thakare, S. M. Sarap, 2023**, Comparative Economics Of Farming System In Jalna District, Vol. Xiii, Issue XXXXVI, April 2023 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 650-652.
3. **D.R. Nikam1 and D.D. Pawar2, 2022**, Comparative Economics Of Cotton Cultivation Under Micro-Irrigation System In North Maharashtra, Vol. Xii, Issue XXXXII, APRIL 2022 Multilogic In Science ISSN 2277-7601, Page 22-29.

4. **Gandhre, A. P. and U. T. Dangore (2021)**. Economics of Bt cotton in Wardha district. *International Journal of Researches in Biosciences, Agriculture and Technology*, 1(9): 60-72.
5. **Manjunath, K., P.S. Dhananjaya Swamy, Jamkhandi B. R. and N. N. Nadoni (2011)** Resource Use Efficiency of Bt-Cotton and Non-Bt Cotton in Haveli District of Karnataka. *International Journal of Agriculture and Food Science Technology*, 4 (3): 253- 258.
6. **More M.S., and Shende N .V. (2021)**. Resource productivity and resource use efficiency in cotton production. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 10(6): 124 -126.
7. **Priyadarshini, B.J., D.K. Sinha, N. Ahmed and K.M. Singh. (2022)**Economic Analysis cotton production in Bhadradi kothagudem district of Telangana. *Biological forum -An International journal* 14(1): 1751-1756.
8. **Ramappa, K.B., Jadhav, V. and Manjunatha, A.V. (2020)**. Comparative economics of Neem coated urea vis-a-vis normal urea: evidence from a field-based study in the Indian context. *Economic Affairs*, 65(2): 275-284.
9. **Shelke, R.D., Bhogaonkar, M.M. and Chavan, R.V. (2016)**. Cost, returns and profitability of Bt-cotton production in beed district. *International Journal of Commerce and Business Management*. 9(1): 58-61.